

Chemical Constituents of the Leaves of *Ichnocarpus frutescens* R. Br.

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Ichnocarpus frutescens R. Br. (Apocynaceae) commonly known as *Siamlata*, is an evergreen, climbing and much branched shrub. It is considered to be an important drug in the indigenous system of treatment¹.

A survey of literature revealed that different parts of this plant have been chemically examined and reported to contain β -sitosterol (roots)², apigenin, luteolin, vanillic acid, syringic acid, protocatechuic acid and sinapic acid (leaves)³, quercetin, quercetin-3- β -D-glucopyranoside (fresh flowers)⁴, L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-glucopyranosyl-1-(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -myrin (stem)⁵, α -myrin acetate, lupeol, lupeol acetate, friedelin, epifriedinol, β -sitosterol (stem)⁶, 6,8,8-trimethylpentacosan-7-one (stem)⁷, Δ^{12} -dehydrolupenyl-3- β -palmitate, lupeol acetate, friedelin, friedelinol, Δ^{12} -dehydrolupeol, oleanolic acid, nonane, 5-hydroxyoctacosan-25-one, dotriacontanoic acid, sitosterol and sitosterol-palmitate (whole plant)⁸. However, fresh leaves collected from Sanai, a village in Tehsil-Bilari, District-Moradabad, on chemical examination gave entirely different results. The major isolable compounds were identified as ursolic acid, kaempferol, trifolin and mannitol. It is interesting to note that none of these four compounds have been reported earlier from any other parts of this plant.

The ethanolic concentrate (85 g) from dried leaves powder (600 g), on petrol extraction gave a petrol-soluble product F-1 (10 g). The petrol-

insoluble mass was resolved into water insoluble F-2 (20 g) and water soluble F-3 (55 g) fractions. F-2 on successive extraction with chloroform and solvent ether gave F-2C and F-2E respectively. F-3 was subjected to successive liquid-liquid extraction with petrol (b.p. 60–80°), ether, ethyl acetate (LL-EA) and butanol (LL-B). Petrol and ether extracts did not yield any products.

F-1 after redissolving in petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) was left in a refrigerator for a week. The resulting green solid (750 mg) on acetylation gave a colourless compound, m.p. 292°; ¹H nmr (CDCl₃) δ 0.7–1.0 (7 \times CH₃), 2.0 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 4.46 (1H, t, H-3), 5.26 (1H, m, H-12); *m/z* 498 (*M*⁺), 438, 249, 248, 203, 189. On methylation it gave an acetyl methyl ester, m.p. 210°; ¹H nmr (CDCl₃) δ 0.72–1.02 (7 \times CH₃), 2.0 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 3.6 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.40 (1H, m, H-3), 5.20 (1H, m, H-12); *m/z* 512 (*M*⁺), 452, 262, 249, 203, 189. On the basis of these data, the parent compound was identified as ursolic acid. Fraction F-2C also on usual work up gave ursolic acid acetate.

Fraction F-2E was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel. The first two fractions (100 ml each) of benzene-ethyl acetate eluate (9 : 1) on crystallisation from aqueous methanol gave a tlc pure compound (50 mg), m.p. 246–47°; λ_{\max} 268, 294 (inf), 322 (inf), 368 (MeOH); 260 (inf), 268, 303 (inf), 350,

421 (AlCl₃); 269, 303 (inf), 348, 421 (AlCl₃/HCl); 275, 303, 387 (NaOAc); 267, 297 (inf), 320 (inf), 371 nm (NaOAc/H₃BO₃); *m/z* 268 (*M*⁺), 258, 153, 134, 121. On acetylation it gave an acetyl derivative, m.p. 118°; ¹H nmr (CDCl₃) δ 2.3 (9H, s, 3 × OCOCH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 6.8 (d, *J* 2 Hz, H-6), 7.7 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 7.3 (3H, m, H-8, H-3', H-5'). On the basis of these data, it was identified as kaempferol.

The fraction LL-EA was extracted with dry acetone and filtered. The acetone solution was concentrated to a small volume and left at room temperature when a paper chromatography pure yellow crystalline flavonoidal compound (200 mg) was obtained, m.p. 248–50°, which gave positive Molisch's test; λ_{max} 266.8, 351 (MeOH); 274, 303.2, 350, 396 (AlCl₃); 273.5, 302.8, 345.6, 394.4 (AlCl₃/HCl); 274.5, 301.7, 338.5 (inf), 371.8 (NaOAc); 266.6, 302.3 (inf), 351.1 nm (NaOAc/H₃BO₃). On acetylation it gave an acetyl derivative, m.p. 110°; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 1.9–2.1 (12H, 4 × OCOCH₃), 2.35 (6H, s, 2 × OCOCH₃), 2.45 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 3.85 (CH₂), 5.0–6.0 (m, carbiny proton), 6.8 (d, *J*, 2 Hz, H-6), 7.3 (3H, m, H-8, H-3', H-5'), 8.0 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-2', H-6'); *m/z* (molecular ion peak not observed), 412, 370, 328, 286, 258, 153, 134, 121. On hydrolysing the parent compound by Killiani mixture and usual processing, the aglycone (5 mg) was identified as kaempferol and the sugar identified as galactose. On the basis of these data the parent glycoside was identified as kaempferol-3-galactoside (trifolin).

The butanol layer LL-B after concentrating to a small volume was left in a refrigerator for a week. A light brown solid (1.5 g) deposited in the flask was crystallised from dilute alcohol

after animal charcoal treatment to give a sweet tasting colourless crystalline compound, m.p. 163–64° (acetate m.p. 110°). It gave a positive test for polyhydric alcohols. On comparing physical properties of the parent compound and its acetate with those of mannitol and its hexaacetate (m.p., m.m.p., co-pc and superimposable ir spectra) the parent compound was identified as mannitol. Final identity of all the compounds was established by comparison with authentic samples.

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